

EXPECTATIONS AND REALITY OF UPSCALED PHYTOREMEDIATION FIELD TRIALS

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ABSTRACT: Despite a plethora of scientific papers on phytoremediation, there is still a scarcity of phytoremediation projects that have been implemented on a full scale. This indicates a knowledge gap regarding whether the phytoremediation capacity obtained in a controlled environment can also be obtained under genuine conditions. The aim of this study is to discuss the differences between pot tests conducted in greenhouse conditions and follow-up field trials conducted at a historically contaminated site that both use the same set of fertilizers, microbiological additives, and plant species.

Keywords: phytoremediation, energy plants, soil contamination, organic pollutants

1 INTRODUCTION

Phytoremediation is recommended as an environmentally friendly and cost-effective technology for the treatment of contaminated soil. However, despite the existence of many scientific papers and reports on phytoremediation, very few full-scale phytoremediation projects have been implemented (see Figure 1). A quick search was performed using the ScienceDirect database to find out how many articles on phytoremediation were published from 2000 to 2022. The search was firstly carried out by using only one keyword, i.e., “phytoremediation”, and then, secondly, by using additional keywords that were added stepwise, resulting in “phytoremediation + field trial” and “phytoremediation + field trial + energy plants”. The first and most noticeable observation from this search is that there is a large discrepancy between the number of publications about phytoremediation in general and the number of publications about phytoremediation performed in field trials. The second observation is that most publications on phytoremediation in field trials have been carried out using energy plants, which could seem to mean that only the added value of energy plants enables the feasibility of this technology.

Figure 1: Search results for papers on phytoremediation according to ScienceDirect database, performed on the 10th of May 2023

It is already general knowledge that the key advantages of phytoremediation are as follows: (i.) it is budgetfriendly, (ii.) it requires minimal equipment and labour, (iii.) it is aesthetically friendly and is supported by the community, (iv.) it reduces soil erosion, and (v.) it reduces both leaching and the spread of contaminants. The main shortcomings of phytoremediation are as follows: (i.) it is a long-term process, (ii) it involves the

incomplete removal of pollutants, (iii.) it entails the undefined handling of post-remediation biomass, and (iv.) it involves a risk of contaminants entering the food chain.

Even though conventional methods for site clean-up, such as soil excavation or soil washing, can grant the site owner a quick fix with minimal expenses, it is widely acknowledged that such conventional methods are also invasive and do not solve the problem, only moving it to another place. Therefore, phytoremediation is becoming widely recognized for its ability to attenuate contaminated soil in a gentle manner, despite being a long-term process. Furthermore, when phytoremediation is coupled with energy plants, it can add to the production of green energy (e.g., biodiesel, syngas) or carbon-enriched biochar. When contaminants exceed the limit values in the soil, such soil cannot be used for food production, and, therefore, growing energy crops that simultaneously attenuate the contaminated soil is a win-win situation in terms of avoiding land competition for agricultural purposes and also for improving the quality of the soil.

The main concerns hindering the wider application of phytoremediation on the field scale are twofold: (i.) how to calculate the rate of removal of contaminants and (ii.) how to assess how many years are needed to achieve good quality of soil. For this reason, more field-scale trials need to be performed in order to ensure the validation and valorization of the phytoremediation process.

The ‘Phy2Climate’ project aims to provide clean biofuel production and phytoremediation solutions from contaminated lands worldwide, and pot tests and field trials are an integral part of the project. The aim of this study is to discuss the differences between pot tests in greenhouse conditions and follow-up field trials at a historically contaminated site.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the contaminated site, subdivision into experimental parcels, and selection of plants

The contaminated site is in mid-Lithuania in the city of Siauliai, which is contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH). In the Soviet era, this site served as an oil base, and it was abandoned after 1990, although the last oil tanks were only removed in 2009. Since then, the site has been left unused. A primary eco-geological survey carried out in 2014 showed that the concentration

of TPH in the soil samples varied from 1,566 mg kg⁻¹ to 17,760 mg kg⁻¹ [1], which, according to Lithuanian and EU legislation, exceeds the limit values up to 22 times [2].

Today, the territory of the former oil base falls in the water intake sanitary protection zone of Siauliai (a city with about 104 000 inhabitants as of 2023). Industrial activities in this zone are prohibited to protect the water from chemical, biological, or physical contamination. The nearest artesian well is only about 55 m away from the site, and the groundwater plate lays below the territory, at a depth of 1.1-2.2m. Up until today, no remediation activities have been carried out at the site.

The area of the contaminated site is about 2400 m². Initial soil characterization was carried out in 2021. Based on the level and depth of the contamination, the site was subdivided into 3 experimental parcels. The parcel(P3) with the most shallow contamination (0-40 cm) was intended for Jerusalem artichoke (parcel size—870 m²); the parcel(P1) with a deeper laying contamination (0-60 cm) was intended for amaranth (parcel size—310 m²); and the parcel(P2) with the deepest contamination (up to 100 cm) was intended for the herbaceous plant mix (parcel size—1230 m²).

The selection of plant species was based on the literature review, where it was stated that the dense and fibrous root system and the rapid growth of the selected plant species can be utilized for efficient degradation/removal of TPHs. These plant species are known to be tolerant in soil of poor quality [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. In addition, Jerusalem artichoke, amaranth, and the selected herbaceous plant species are common in Lithuania, so the agrotechnical means to cultivate them are also well established.

2.2 Characterization of the contaminated soil

The primary eco-geological survey of the site was carried out in 2014. The site was surveyed following the State plan to identify contaminated areas all over Lithuania. At the Siauliai site, there were three groundwater sampling points with an average borehole depth of 6 m; four surface soil sampling points with an average depth of 0.05-0.25 m; and, finally, three deep soil sampling points where the sampling depth ranged from 2.1 m to 8.25 m. The sampling points were placed to reflect the eco-geological situation in the main transit areas of possible contamination with oil products, heavy metals, and sediment, as well as to accurately determine the direction of the groundwater flow and the hydraulic gradients in addition to the geological structure of the studied area.

Soil characterization under the 'Phy2Climate' project was carried out in 2021. As mentioned above, the site was divided into 3 parcels based on the findings of the eco-geological survey from 2014. In every parcel, 3 sampling boreholes were made using a stainless steel hand auger. Joint soil samples at 4 depths (0-20 cm, 20-40 cm, 60-80 cm, and 60-100 cm) were made for every square. In total, 12 joint samples were prepared and transported to certified laboratories for further analysis.

2.3 Potexperiment

The main objective of the potexperiment was to evaluate the potential to degrade TPH and other organic substances in contaminated soil using a combination of plants, biological additives, and nutrients specially designed for this purpose. Jerusalem artichoke, amaranth,

and three mixes of herbaceous plant species were selected for testing in the potexperiment under greenhouse conditions in 2021.

Three mixes of herbaceous plants were used in the potexperiment, where a single mix comprised at least four different plant species. During the pot trial, the aim was to determine which mix or even which species are more suitable for TPH degradation, so that in the upcoming field trial, only one mix with the highest degradation potential would be used.

Contaminated soil was brought from Siauliai following the subdivision into three parcels. It was difficult to find control (i.e., clean) soil that would exhibit the same soil parameters as the contaminated batch. Thus, clean soil, identified as sandy loam, was taken from arable land and then mixed with sand in order to resemble the granulometric composition of the contaminated soil.

A biological additive was used to enhance the degradation of organic pollutants. The additive is a powdered biological material consisting of a blend of *Bacillus spp.*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, and *Rhodococcus spp.*

To increase the organic content in the contaminated soil, vermicompost was used. The vermicompost contained at least 34% organic matter (OM), and levels of NPK were 1.5%, 1.5%, and 2.1%, respectively.

Mineral fertilizers were used to increase the macronutrient pool. Agriculturally conventional amounts of N, P, K, and S deriving from urea (N: 46.2%), ammonium sulphate (N: 21%, S-24%), NPK(S) 15%-15%-15% (S: 11.5%), and KCl (K: 60%) were added to the contaminated soil.

Plastic (HDPE) boxes were used for growing the plants. Each box contained about 60 kg of fresh soil, and the experiment was carried out in triplicate. The surface area of each box was 0.1725 m². All the additives were added to the contaminated soil before seeding the seeds. The control soil was not amended. Tap water was used for watering the plants.

Four tubers of Jerusalem artichoke were planted in every box. The tubers weighed about 10-20 g each. About 220 seeds of amaranth were used for one box. While for the herbaceous plant mixes, the composition was as follows: MIX I: tall fescue (35%), perennial ryegrass (30%), reed canary grass (10%), and red clover (25%); MIX II: annual ryegrass (10%), meadow fescue (35%), meadow foxtail (10%), alfa alfa (25%), and common bird's trefoil (20%); and MIX III: festulolium (20%), common bent (15%), white clover (20%), and honey clover (35%).

The potexperiment was carried out under greenhouse conditions from April to October in 2021. Soil characterization, including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), macronutrient concentration, OM content, microbial biomass, and TPH level, was undertaken before and after the potexperiment.

Germination tests on the seeds of amaranth and herbaceous species were carried out before the start of the potexperiment. During the experiment, plant height and lushness was evaluated on several occasions. Aboveground biomass for herbaceous plants was cut three times and then summarized. The Jerusalem artichoke was cut at the end of the growing season in October, and the biomass was split into tubers and stalks. The amaranth, meanwhile, was cut in September, and only the aboveground part was evaluated for the biomass output.

2.4 Field trial

The field trial was carried out at the Siauliai site. The start of the field trial was in May 2022, and the trial is planned for three consecutive years. The site was cleared of bushes, stones, and litter in 2021 followed by deep tillage and harrowing in 2022. Then, based on the subdivision into parcels and assignation to certain plant species, the parcels were amended as follows: the parcel for herbaceous plants was amended with vermicompost (4.8 t ha⁻¹), NPK(S) 12%-11%-18% (S: 8%, 0.2 t/ha) and KCl (K: 60%, 0.064 t/ha); the parcel for amaranth was amended with vermicompost (13.5 t ha⁻¹), NPK(S) 12%-11%-18% (S: 8%, 0.8 t/ha); and the parcel for Jerusalem artichoke was amended with vermicompost (8.9 t ha⁻¹), NPK(S) 12%-11%-18% (S: 8%, 0.6 t/ha).

The herbaceous plant mix was seeded by hand and the soil surface was slightly raked after the seeds were spread. The mix comprised 37.5% tall fescue (68 kg ha⁻¹), 25% perennial ryegrass (4.5 kg ha⁻¹), 25% alfa alfa (4.5 kg ha⁻¹), 6.25% festuca perennis (1.1 kg ha⁻¹), and 6.25% bird'sfoot trefoil (1.1 kg ha⁻¹). Amaranth was also seeded by hand and the surface was slightly raked after the seeds were spread. For amaranth, about 580 g was seeded in the assigned parcel (18 kg ha⁻¹). The Jerusalem artichoke was planted in its assigned parcel, and about 100 kg ww of planting material was used in the parcel (1.1 t ww ha⁻¹). Tubers were planted using a shovel at a depth of 0.10-0.15 m. Distance between tubers in a row was ~0.4 m, and the distance between the rows was 0.7 m.

Artificial irrigation was not applied during the field trials, nor were pesticides used.

The same bacterial additive as in the pot experiment was spread out in mid-June 2022. About 100 kg (dw) of the additive was added to a tank (12 m³) with lukewarm water for activation. Additionally, meat and bone meal were added to the tank to enhance activation of the bacteria. The mixture was aerated and then poured onto the soil.

The herbaceous plants were cut in August, and the amaranth and the Jerusalem artichoke were cut in September. Plant height and lushness were monitored through the growing season. Soil samples were taken in October after harvesting the Jerusalem artichoke. The sampling was performed in the same manner as during the initial characterization at four depths.

2.5 Evaluation of phytoremediation process

Phytoremediation performance was evaluated regarding aspects such as changes in the soil parameters, including general soil parameters and contaminants, biomass output, and cost.

Inorganic contaminants, such as heavy metals, enter plants through the root system, and they can be accumulated in the root zone or transported into the aboveground parts. Organic contaminants that are lipophilic and hydrophobic in nature are not usually taken up by plants if they do not come into direct contact with the plant either as liquid or in vapor form from the atmosphere [10]. Thus, the calculation of translocation and/or bioaccumulation factors that are conventionally used for heavy metals is not possible in the case of TPH. In this case, relative phytoremediation (efficiency) potential was calculated as a ratio between the TPH concentration in the soil before the phytoremediation and the TPH concentration in the soil after phytoremediation and expressed as a percentage.

Finally, based on the expenses needed to manage the

phytoremediation field trial of 2400 m² size, the cost that would be necessary to administrate 1 ha was calculated using the database for sustainable agriculture at <https://www.ktbl.de/>.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Changes in soil parameters

Initial soil characterization was carried out at the Siauliai site in three boreholes at four depths in 2021. Table I presents the level of contamination with TPH in the three parcels. The results are well in line with the history of the site. The heaviest contamination was detected in parcels where the oil tanks were mounted. Due to both careless handling of oil products back when the oil base was still in use and then oil spillages when the tanks were dismantled, some spots in P1 exhibited pools of oil visible to the naked eye. In addition, there was a very distinct odour of oil when the samples were taken. The P1 and P2 parcels have a deep-laying contamination because surplus amounts of oil have seeped into the ground over the years, while the P3 parcel, where oil tanks were not built, has only top-layer contamination that probably results from smaller accident spills or cross-contamination from truck tires. Lastly, the limit value for petroleum hydrocarbons in soil set by Lithuanian legislation is 200 mg kg⁻¹, meaning that in some places (and depths), the soil at the Siauliai site exceeds the limit value by up to 35 times.

Polyaromatic hydrocarbons as well as heavy metals were also checked in the soil from the Siauliai site, but all were either below detection limits or within the limits of background values.

Table I: TPH fractions detected during the initial soil characterization (n=1, joint samples).

Parcel and sampling depth, cm	TPH, mg kg ⁻¹ DW
P1 0-20	685
P1 20-40	3753
P1 40-60	7132
P1 60-100	2492
P2 0-20	245
P2 20-40	790
P2 40-60	1029
P2 60-100	557
P3 0-20	698
P3 20-40	431
P3 40-60	<100
P3 60-100	<100
Limit value	200

Table II shows general soil parameters determined during the initial characterization of the soil samples from the Siauliai site. The soil was critically depleted in terms of organic matter and the main macronutrients, especially N. For this reason, mineral and organic fertilizers were used both at the pot experiment and during the field trials. The amounts of the applied fertilizers were calculated based on conventional fertilization rates used in traditional agriculture.

Table II: Average soil parameters detected during the initial soil characterization after the potexperiment and after the field trials (the first year), (n=12).

Analyte	Initial	After potexperiment	After field trial
N, mg kg ⁻¹	5.4	1373	961
P, mg kg ⁻¹	354	130	64
K, mg kg ⁻¹	1493	364	185
Mg, mg kg ⁻¹	8841	544	306
OM, %	2.6	4.8	3.8
Total C, %	2.9	18.8	3.9
pH	8.2	8.6	8.4
EC, mS m ⁻¹	10.9	86	14.5
Microbial activity, CPU/ml	1.9·10 ⁵	1.3·10 ⁵	4.2·10 ⁵

Changes in soil parameters after the potexperiment and after the field trials (Table II) show similar tendencies. Total N content increased about 200 times, which can be attributed both to the fertilization and to the increased N accumulation rate in the soil due to increased microbial activity. Total K and P content dropped after the growing season in both cases despite the fertilization. Magnesium was not added through fertilization, but plants depleted its pool significantly over one growing season. Despite the addition of vermicompost, the content of OM increased only slightly. This is in line with the pH values, as it did not drop despite the addition of the vermicompost, which has an acidic nature.

To sum up, this indicates the need to both monitor macronutrient content in the soil and fertilize phytoremediation trials in order to sustain the efficiency of the process.

3.2 Phytoremediation potential

Figure 2 shows the reduction of TPH in the soil after the potexperiment using amaranth, Jerusalem artichoke, and three mixes of herbaceous plants species. Figure 3 shows the total (as a sum of concentrations from all depths) reduction of TPH in the soil after the field trials (the first year) where amaranth and Jerusalem artichoke were grown but where only one mix of herbaceous plant species was seeded.

Table I outlined that soil contamination at the Siauliai site with TPH is the highest in the P1 parcel that was dedicated to the herbaceous plant mix, lower in the P2 parcel that was dedicated to amaranth, and the lowest in the P3 parcel dedicated to Jerusalem artichoke. The graphs represent different starting concentrations of TPH. This is due to the fact that the contaminated soil for the pot experiment was taken from the top layer (0-40 cm) and is thus lower. The TPH content presented in Figure 2, meanwhile, is in line with Table I.

The biggest reduction of TPH was observed where the contamination was the highest. During the potexperiment, herbaceous plants reduced about 82% of TPH, and there was no significant difference between the mixes, i.e., the composition of the mixes. As for amaranth, it reduced the TPH content by 41%, while Jerusalem artichoke reduced the TPH content by 22%. Despite the success of the phytoremediation process though, it is still clear that one year was not sufficient to reach the limit value of 200 mg kg⁻¹.

Figure 3: Reduction of TPH concentration in soil after the field trials (the first year).

Growing herbaceous plants in contaminated soil during the field trials reduced the total TPH content by almost 50%. Growing amaranth and Jerusalem artichoke did not have any effect on the TPH content. Here, as well as in the case of the potexperiment, one year was insufficient to reach the limit values.

It remains unclear whether the reduction of TPH content is dependent on the plant species, meaning that the herbaceous species have superior qualities over the amaranth and Jerusalem artichoke. Furthermore, the scientific literature does not provide a credible explanation as to whether the TPH content can be reduced entirely or only to a certain extent.

Such uncertainties pose serious difficulties to both extrapolating contaminant removal rates and estimating the number of growing cycles needed to clean up the soil.

3.3 Biomass output

The germination of seeds was tested before the potexperiment to evaluate whether contamination influences plant development at the initial growing stages. In the case of amaranth and Jerusalem artichoke, there were no significant differences between the germination rates. For amaranth, the germination rate was 42.9%–46.6%, and for Jerusalem artichoke, it was 100%.

For the herbaceous plant MIX I, the germination rate was 44.3% and 68.4%, for MIX II it was 59.5% and 61.7%, and for MIX III it was 14.3% and 21.8% when the plants were grown on the contaminated soil and the clean soil (control), respectively. This shows that the selected species had different tolerance levels to the contamination. Furthermore, there were species, such as red clover, meadow foxtail, common bent, and honey clover, that did not germinate at all. However, these species did not germinate in the clean soil either,

although they were eliminated from the species mix intended for the field trials.

The height of the plants was measured during the potexperiment (Table III), and this revealed that in all cases, plants grown on the contaminated soil developed higher stems and more biomass. The boxes used during the potexperiment contained about 60 kg of soil and its surface area was 0.1725 m². During one growing season, MIX I produced a total (per triplicate) of 0.215 kg and 0.169 kg of biomass, MIX II produced a total of 0.201 kg and 0.192 kg of biomass, and MIX III produced a total of 0.185 kg and 0.161 kg of biomass when grown on the contaminated and the clean soil, respectively.

In the case of Jerusalem artichoke, the stem length did not differ between plants grown on the contaminated and the clean soil—it was about 160 cm on average. Tuber mass was significantly higher for the plants from the contaminated soil, though—on average, 39.8 g per tuber. For tubers from the clean soil, the mass was only 27.9 g per tuber. The total biomass of Jerusalem artichoke (per triplicate) was 1.2 kg for the contaminated soil and 0.6 kg for the clean soil.

Amaranth grown on the contaminated soil had higher stems (185 cm), while that grown on the clean soil had lower stems (135 cm). The total production (per triplicate) of amaranth was 1.3 kg and 0.5 kg, respectively, for the contaminated and the clean soils.

Overall, the potexperiment was carried out without major drawbacks, and surprisingly good development of all plant species on the contaminated soil allowed us to predict potential biomass output from 1 ha, as given in Table IV for the expected yield based on the potexperiment.

Table III: Average stem height of plants during the potexperiment (n=3).

	Species	Height of the stems, cm	
		Contaminated soil	Clean soil
MIX I	Tall fescue	53.0	37.9
	Perennial ryegrass	43.9	35.9
	Reed canary grass	63.6	46.1
	Red clover	-	21.8
MIX II	Annual ryegrass	50.8	40.0
	Meadow fescue	27.8	35.2
	Meadow foxtail	-	-
	Alfalfa	54.1	38.7
MIX III	Birdsfoot trefoil	52.7	28.0
	Festulolium	43.4	32.5
	Tall fescue	70.1	41.6
	Common bent	-	-
MIX III	White clover	54.1	14.1
	Honey clover	-	-

However, the expectations were met only in the case of herbaceous plants, but the Jerusalem artichoke and amaranth harvests were drastically smaller. For Jerusalem artichoke, plant density played a major part, as it dropped more than 20 times in the field compared to the pot experiments (23 plants m⁻² versus 5 plants m⁻²). Density was high in the pot tests and did not affect the development of the plant, but it needed to be adjusted (dropped) in the field to fit agricultural machinery dimensions.

Table IV: Estimation on biomass yields.

Biomass yield type	Herbaceous plants (P1)	Amaranth (P2)	J. artichoke (P3)
Total biomass yield from the field trials, t/parcel dw	0.16	0.04	0.34
Calculated yield based on the field trials, tha ⁻¹ dw	1.3	1.4	11.7
Expected yield based on the pot-experiment, tha ⁻¹ dw	1.2	27.1	23.5

In the case of amaranth, prolonged dry conditions slowed down the germination of seeds and allowed the spread of and eventual overshadowing by weeds, which are typically more resistant to unfavourable weather conditions. Furthermore, it was later discovered that poor-quality amaranth seed was used in the field trials, which resulted in poor plant development and low density.

Unlike the monocultures, the herbaceous mix comprised five different species, and it is likely that it allowed better adaptability to harsh conditions. Thus, it was possible to achieve the yield as estimated.

3.4 Cost

To install and maintain phytoremediation field trials at the Siauliai site, the following operations were needed for all three plant cultures: deep power harrowing and levelling, spreading of fertilizers, soil cultivation and seed preparation, application of mineral fertilizers, sowing (seeding), roll-towing, application of bacterial additive, cutting down plants, turning biomass with a rotary tedder, windrowing, and bale pressing. In addition, tuber digging was necessary for Jerusalem artichoke. The cost can be split into four large blocks: (i.) consumables (seeds, fertilizers, bacterial additive, etc.), (ii.) diesel consumption, (iii.) labour (for operating the machinery), and (iv.) crop monitoring. Some operations, like power harrowing, were needed only during the first year when installing the field trials. Table V shows the actual costs that would be needed to apply phytoremediation to 1 ha using either the herbaceous plant mix, Jerusalem artichoke, or amaranth. The overall cost between the different plant cultures does not pose significant differences. However, in an ideal scenario, Jerusalem artichoke and amaranth would produce higher biomass yield than herbaceous plants and the return would be greater. Figure 4 shows that the main share of the cost goes to consumables. In the case of this study, bacterial additive was used, and the market price for this product is 28 EUR per kg⁻¹. About 400 kg of bacterial additive should be used for 1 ha to enhance the degradation of TPH. The use of bacterial additive would consume about 50% of the estimated budget, and, thus, the use of any additive should be carefully evaluated.

Table V: Estimated cost needed to remediate 1 ha of contaminated soil in euros.

Type of cost	Herbaceous plants	Jerusalem artichoke	Amaranth
Consumables	13953	15444	14324
Diesel	3445	3553	3464
Labour	214	325	201
Monitoring	1152	1296	1296
TOTAL	18764	20618	19285

Figure 4: Analysis of the cost needed to remediate 1 ha of contaminated soil.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A complex, including specially selected plants, mineral and organic fertilizers, and bacterial additive, was applied to the field. The effectiveness of this complex has been proved under greenhouse conditions. Overall, the potexperiment was carried out without major drawbacks, and surprisingly good development of all plant species on the contaminated soil allowed us to predict potentially high biomass output from the field trials. However, the expectations were only met in the case of the herbaceous plants. Poor quality amaranth seed, unfavourable weather conditions, and the reduced planting density of Jerusalem artichoke resulted in significantly lower yields. The herbaceous plants also exhibited a high TPH reduction rate. About 50% of TPH were degraded during the first year, although this is still far below the limit values. Furthermore, soil analysis indicated the need to monitor macronutrient content in the soil at least yearly and to fertilize phytoremediation trials in order to sustain the efficiency of the process. Cost analysis revealed that it takes about EUR 20,000 to remediate 1 ha of contaminated soil. However, the cost could be reduced if scrutinizing the use of expensive additives. To finalize, although not all expectations were met during the first year of the experiment, the application of phytoremediation in the field scale seems feasible.

As a final note, the biomass obtained during the field trials was collected, dried out, pelletized, and forwarded to one of the “Phy2Climate” partners to be further utilized in biofuel production.

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